

artificially salinized (pH 8.7, ECe 5.2 dS/m, SAR 44.6, ESP 39.6, TSS 42.6, Ca^{++} + Mg^{++} 5.5, and Na^+ 71.6 meq/liter. Arti-

ficial salinity was developed by adding a 1:4:5:10 of magnesium sulfate, sodium chloride, calcium chloride, and sodium

sulfate — salts usually present in saline soils of Pakistan. The crop was irrigated from a tubewell with saline sodic water containing HCO_3 meq/liter, TSS 35 meq/liter (Ca^{++} + Mg^{++} 4.8, Na^+ 30.2) with a SAR of 19.5. Net plot size per entry was 4 m². Hills of one seedling each were spaced at 23 x 23 cm in a completely randomized block design with four replications.

NR74-108 yielded significantly more than the other strains, including Damodar and Getu (Table 2). NR74-108 is a semi-tall rice with stiff straw and medium-long grain that does not shatter. It flowers in 121 d. It may be suitable for cultivation on marginal saline soils and may be used as a donor of salt tolerance genes. □

Table 1. Response of plant progenies to salinity^a (percent reduction over control^b).

Cultivar	Florets/ panicle	Panicle fertility (%)	Yield per plant (g/m ²)
NR74-79	15 g	9 g	42 h
NR74-92	38 ab	20 b	70 b
NR74-93	33 cd	13 ef	61 e
NR74-96	36 bc	16 cd	65 d
NR74-97	30 d	15 de	67 cd
NR74-106	37 b	18 bc	54 f
NR74-108	18 f	13 f	49 g
Jhona 349 (resistant parent)	25 e	20 b	68 bc
Magnolia (susceptible parent)	40 a	30 a	80 a

^apH 8.7, ECe 7.2 dS/m at 25°C, SAR 59.7, ESP 44.3. ^bpH 7.7, ECe 2.3 dS/m at 25°C, SAR 8.4, ESP 12.0. Figures followed by different letters are significantly different at 5% level of significance.

Table 2. Performance of salt-tolerant rice strains in saline fields.^a

Cultivar	Yield g/m ²	Plant ht (cm)	Productive tillers/ plant	Panicles/m ²	Days to flowering	Panicle length (cm)	Florets/ panicle	Panicle fertility (%)	1000- grain wt (g)
NR74-108	34 a	101 b	10 cd	228 e	121 c	25 ab	109 d	89 a	23 ab
NR74-79	32 b	111 a	11 bc	252 d	125 b	27 a	135 b	84 bc	23 a
Damodar	28 c	93 d	14 a	333 b	120 c	20 cde	127 c	86 ab	15 d
Giza 159	21 d	74 e	12 ab	285 c	117 d	22 bc	133 b	81 d	19 c
Getu	27 c	92 d	13 a	341 a	152 a	21 cd	151 a	82 cd	16 d
Jhona 349	28 f	96 c	8 de	204 f	114 e	18 de	105 e	83 bcd	23 a
Magnolia	17 g	96 c	7 e	184 g	103 f	17 e	103 e	67 e	22 b

^aFigures followed by different letters are significantly different at 5% level.

PBN1, a semidwarf upland rice cultivar tolerant of iron deficiency

Y. S. Nerkar, M. B. Misal, and R. V. Marekar, *Genetics and Plant Breeding Department, Marathwada Agricultural University, Parbhani 431402, Maharashtra, India*

PBN1 (Prabhavati) is a semidwarf (75 cm) recommended for cultivation in iron-deficient black soils (calcareous vertisols with 40-65% montmorillonitic clay and pH 8.0-9.2) in Maharashtra State. It is an induced mutant of the tall local cultivar Ambemohor obtained through ethyl methanesulfonate (0.2%) seed treatment.

PBN1 is nitrogen-responsive and is suitable for direct seeding in uplands. It tolerates iron chlorosis and has dark green foliage. Its roots have more efficient iron-

Performance of PBN1 under direct seeding in UVT on irrigated black soils.

Cultivar	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)				Days to maturity	Lodging score ^b
	1980	1981	1982	Weighted mean		
PBN1	2.5	3.1	4.1	3.3	119	0
PBN4	1.7	2.4	3.1	2.5	117	1
PBN7	2.1	2.6	3.3	2.8	116	0
PBN20	1.5	2.6	2.8	2.4	119	1
PBN30	2.3	2.5	3.3	2.7	115	3
Ambemohor (local)	2.3	2.4	3.4	2.8	116	4
Jalgaon 5	2.3	2.9	3.2	2.9	116	4
Tuljapur 1	2.6	2.5	3.0	2.7	113	4
SE ±	0.21	0.26	0.34	0.24		
CD (0.05)	0.64	0.81	0.97	0.73		

^aAv of 3 sites. ^bBy the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

reductive capacity than high yielding semidwarfs with Dee-geo-woo-gen in their parentage. Maturity ranges from 115 to 120 days, which helps it fit well in the rice — wheat, rice — legume, or rice — oil-seed double-cropping sequence in the

canal command areas. Grain is medium coarse, translucent, and scented.

PBN1 was evaluated under direct seeding in uniform variety trials (irrigated black soils) at three sites for three seasons (see table). It yielded 20% more than the

local check Ambemohor (see table). In minikit trials conducted in farmer fields

in 1981 (28 trials in 3 districts) and 1982 (76 trials in 6 districts), PBN1 yielded 2.5

t/ha in 1981 and 4.1 t/ha in 1982. Ambemohor yielded 2.3 and 3.4 t/ha. □

Screening rice varieties for salt tolerance in Bangladesh

G. J. U. Ahmed and K. U. Ahmed, *BRR1 Regional Station, Sonagazi, Noakhali, Bangladesh*

Salinity limits rice cultivation on about 1 million ha of land in southern Bangladesh.

We developed a simple, low-cost screening method to identify rice varieties with salt tolerance. Nearly neutral dried

Table 1. Salt-tolerant varieties or lines isolated in Bangladesh.

Variety, line	Score ^a
<i>Aus</i>	
BR1	3
BR203-26-2	3
BR201-193-1	4
IR9884-54-3 (resistant check)	3
Pajam (susceptible check)	9
<i>Aman</i>	
BR4	4
BR10	4
Rajalsail	3
Kajalsail	3
IR9884-54-3 (resistant check)	3
Pajam (susceptible check)	9

^aVisual scoring 1-9: 1-4 = almost healthy plant, 7-9 = almost dead plant.

soil was placed in a petri dish and an NaCl solution was added to the soil to adjust the electrical conductivity to 10 dS/m and salinity level was monitored throughout the experiment. Twenty seeds of each variety or line were sown in the petri dish. IR9884-54-3 was used as resistant check and Pajam, the susceptible check. Germinated seeds were grown in the petri dish 21 d. Salt injury was scored by the IRRI Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

In the 1982 screening of 50 varieties or lines, 3 aus season varieties (BR1, BR203-26-2, and BR201-193-1) and 4

aman varieties (BR4, BR10, Rajalsail, and Kajalsail) were salt tolerant (Table 1).

Those varieties and lines were tested in a saline field in replicated yield trials. In 1983 aus, BR201-193-1 and BR203-26-2 were tested with local check variety Chicknal. They were direct seeded by dibbling at 20-x 15-cm spacing and fertilizer 60 kg N and 40 kg P/ha were applied. They yielded more than twice the local check variety (Table 2).

In 1983 BR4 and BR10 were tested in t. aman under uniform conditions. The local variety Kajalsail was used as check. BR4 and BR10 yielded best (Table 2). □

Table 2. Yield and related characters of salt-tolerant rice.

Variety, line	Flowering date	Duration (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles/m ²	Yield (t/ha)
<i>Aus^a</i>					
BR201-193-1	7 Jun 83	112	121.0	425	3.96
BR203-26-2	17 Jun 83	127	104.0	457	6.65
Chicknal (check)	15 May 83	90	97.0	247	1.50
<i>Aman^b</i>					
BR4	26 Oct 82	138	102.0	344	3.60
BR10	22 Oct 82	137	98.0	378	4.0
Kajalsail (check)	5 Nov 82	154	140.0	210	1.6

^aSeeded 9 Mar 83. ^bSeeded 30 Jun 82.

Salinity-mediated enhancement of harvest index of rice – selection criterion for salt tolerance

T. N. Singh, *Crop Physiology Department, N. C. University of Agriculture and Technology, Faizabad, U. P., India*

Soil salinity inhibits rice production in almost every country. It is important to develop salt-tolerant rice varieties to increase rice production in areas with saline soil.

We studied the effects of saline soils on harvest index (HI) (grain:straw) of rice at the Salinity Institute, Karnal. Four rice varieties were planted at 5 salinity levels (ECe 1.2, 5.6, 8.7, 13.0 and 16.0 dS/m) in 18-kg porcelain pots. NaCl:CaCl₂ at 4:1 was mixed in sandy loam soil. The soil was saturated and 35-day-old seed-

1. Yield reductions of rice varieties by salinity.

2. Trend of change in harvest index of rice varieties by salinity.